

8T – Diameter & Energy of a Photon

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants series of the 8T and varying curvature, in its first representation, i.e. Bosons as net curvature on the matrix tensor – analysis of the photon will be presented. Author will two options concerning the diameter of the Boson of the third interaction, electromagnetism. First option as the ripple diameter to be time invariant, the other to be time variant.

Introduction

The new 8T framework regard bosons as net curvature on the matrix tensor. The net curvature are of discrete amounts and is isomorphic to the prime numbers or one. That is opposing to fermions, which vanish in even numbers.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7... \quad (1.21)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_1 + 1 \quad (1.3)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 + 1 \quad (1.31)$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_3 + 1 \quad (1.32)$$

The photon is associated with discrete amount of curvature, generated by the invariant (3), and proved the electron. The overall representation gives us the propagation picture for the third coupling term:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.32)$$

Which is represented in the following visually, the photon is a ripple across the matric tensor. Due to its prime number feature, it propagates independently of matter.

The key question is whether the photon has a varying diameter of a fixed diameter. Assuming it is varying overtime, such a claim allow as to correlate its diameter to its energy. The larger the ripple, the longer the wavelength and the lower the energy. That is reasonable to assume as the more of the matric tensor it covers, the more flat it is, i.e. less curved. However, since the photon is associated with a discrete amount of curvature $N_v = (+5)$ there has to be a conservation law. It is possible to state that the net curvature is preserved on the matric tensor, but as time goes, by it covers more and more area of the matric tensor and thus gets weaker.

Additional point to make concerning light is the subject of polarization. We can represent the net curvature as linearly polarized and not as presented above circular ripple of curvature.

Imagine the left edge, as the electron being emitted a certain amount of net curvature on the matric tensor. The net curvature on this scenario is linearly polarized. The main question of this assay is whether the photon diameter can vary over time. According to the new framework the author will provide two predictions:

- (1) The diameter of circularly polarized photon varies overtime and proportional to the time of propagation.
- (2) The amount of net curvature is distributed over the matric tensor. The larger the distribution, the lower the wavelength of the photon. The energy of the photon is inversely proportional to time.

Those predictions would apply to each element in the coupling series, but for simplicity sake, we assume second and above. All bosonic fields are ripples, which are circular due to the fact they are part of a cyclic group, given by equations (1.33-1.34):

$$(e) = (3) \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$$

$$\mathcal{B} = \{N_1 = (+3)\mathcal{M}, N_2 = +(5)\mathcal{M} \dots\} \quad (1.33)$$

$$\mathcal{B} = \{N_1 = (+3)\mathcal{M}, N_2 = +(\gamma)\mathcal{M} \dots\} \quad (1.34)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)
- [2] O. Manor. "The Principle of Least Curvature on Lorentz Manifold" In: (2021)
- [3] O. Manor. "The Coupling Constants Series and Rapid Galaxies Formation" In: (2021)